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MICROBIAL B-GLUCANS: EXTRACTION METHODS AND STRUCTURAL CHARACTERISTICS – A REVIEW

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Abstract. The growing interest in functional food ingredients and sustainable bioresources has increased the scientific focus on microbial β -glucans. These polysaccharides are recognized for their immunomodulatory, antioxidant, and prebiotic activities, with potential to improve human health and support innovative biotechnological applications. The present review is based on the hypothesis that the structural diversity of β -glucans significantly influences both their bioactivity and their suitability for industrial utilization. The main objective is to analyze the extraction and purification methods applied for recovering β -glucans from microbial sources, highlighting the relationship between molecular structure and functional properties. Classical techniques such as hot water and enzymatic extraction are compared with modern strategies including ultrasound-, microwave-, and supercritical fluid-assisted methods. Findings indicate that extraction efficiency, yield, and purity strongly depend on the method employed, while hybrid approaches enhance both bioactivity preservation and environmental sustainability. Microbial β -glucans show promising applications in food, pharmaceutical, biomedical, and cosmetic sectors, while safety considerations regarding microbial contamination and immunogenicity remain essential. The review concludes that advances in processing technologies, together with standardized characterization, will contribute to optimizing β -glucan production and to expanding their role as multifunctional bio-ingredients.

Keywords: *dietary supplements, enzymatic extraction, functional ingredients, immunomodulation, microbial safety, polysaccharides.*

Rezumat. Interesul tot mai mare pentru ingredientele alimentare funcționale și bioresursele sustenabile a intensificat atenția științifică asupra β -glucanilor microbieni. Acești polizaharide sunt recunoscuți pentru activitățile lor imunomodulatoare, antioxidante și prebiotice, având potențialul de a îmbunătăți sănătatea umană și de a sprijini aplicațiile biotehnologice inovatoare. Prezentul studiu se bazează pe ipoteza că diversitatea structurală a β -glucanilor influențează semnificativ atât bioactivitatea acestora, cât și adecvarea lor pentru utilizare industrială. Principalul obiectiv este analiza metodelor de extracție și purificare aplicate pentru obținerea β -glucanilor din surse microbiene, evidențiind relația dintre structura moleculară și proprietățile funcționale. Tehnicile clasice, precum extracția cu

apă fierbinte și extracția enzimatică, sunt comparate cu strategii moderne, care includ metode asistate de ultrasunete, microunde și fluide supercritice. Rezultatele indică faptul că eficiența extracției, randamentul și puritatea depind în mare măsură de metoda utilizată, în timp ce abordările hibride contribuie la păstrarea bioactivității și la creșterea sustenabilității mediului. β -glucanii microbieni prezintă aplicații promițătoare în sectoarele alimentar, farmaceutic, biomedical și cosmetic, însă considerațiile legate de siguranță, precum contaminarea microbială și imunogenicitatea, rămân esențiale. Lucrarea concluzionează că progresele tehnologice în procesare, combinate cu standardizarea metodelor de caracterizare, vor contribui la optimizarea producției de β -glucani și la extinderea rolului acestora ca bioingrediente multifuncționale.

Cuvinte-cheie: *suplimente alimentare, extracție enzimatică, ingrediente funcționale, imunomodulare, siguranță microbială, polizaharide.*

1. Introduction

β -glucans are an important class of polysaccharides, found in some food products such as oats (e.g. oatmeal, oat bran, oat flour), barley (e.g. barley grains, barley bran, barley bakery products), wheat (especially wheat bran, wholemeal bread), rye (e.g. wholemeal bread, bakery products) but also in the cell walls of fungi, yeasts and certain bacteria, such as *Agrobacterium* and *Bacillus* [1,2]. They are composed of β -D-glucose monomers linked by β -(1 \rightarrow 3), β -(1 \rightarrow 4) and/or β -(1 \rightarrow 6) linkages, the specific structure depending on their biological source. Due to their unique molecular configuration, β -glucans interact with immune receptors such as dectin-1 and CR3, stimulating essential immune processes, including phagocytosis, cytokine production, and natural killer cell activation. These interactions confer immunomodulatory, antioxidant, and hypocholesterolemic effects, making β -glucans valuable for applications in the food and pharmaceutical industries as well as in biomedicine. Additionally, β -glucans are incorporated into dietary supplements to enhance resistance to infections and reduce inflammation, emphasizing their potential as functional ingredients with benefits for human health [3,4].

In the pharmaceutical sector, microbial β -glucans are investigated as adjuvants in cancer immunotherapy due to their ability to stimulate macrophages and neutrophils, enhancing the efficacy of monoclonal antibodies and chemotherapeutic agents [5]. Their non-toxic and biodegradable properties also support their use as drug delivery systems, including in the form of nanoparticles and hydrogels for targeted release [6].

In the food sector, β -glucans act as bioactive ingredients, supporting gut health by modulating the microbiota and increasing short-chain fatty acid production, as well as exhibiting hypocholesterolemic effects [7,8]. In cosmetics, β -glucans are valued for their moisturizing, anti-aging properties and for stimulating collagen synthesis, and are included in dermocosmetic formulations [9].

Additionally, due to their biocompatibility and structural characteristics, microbial β -glucans are employed in sustainable materials, such as biodegradable films, wound dressings, and scaffolds for tissue engineering. Microbial production offers advantages such as high reproducibility, scalability, and control over processing conditions, and ongoing research on structure–function relationships and downstream processing is expected to further expand their applications in biomedical, food, and industrial sectors [10,11].

The aim of this study is to highlight the importance of β -glucans as bioactive polysaccharides and to analyze the extraction and purification methods applied for their

recovery from various microbial sources, with a particular focus on *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. The paper seeks to compare the advantages and limitations of different techniques described in the scientific literature, in order to identify effective strategies for maximizing the yield and purity of the extracted compounds. Furthermore, emphasis is placed on the relationship between the structure of β -glucans and their biological activities, to substantiate their applicability in the food, pharmaceutical, biomedical, and cosmetic fields.

2. Structural Properties and Biological Activity

The three-dimensional structure, solubility, molecular weight, and bioactivity directly influence the linkage patterns and branching of β -glucans. The most studied microbial sources are yeasts (*S. cerevisiae*), bacteria (*Bacillus subtilis*, *Agrobacterium*), and filamentous fungi (*Aspergillus*, *Pleurotus*, *Lentinula*) [12].

β -Glucans from *S. cerevisiae* possess a β -(1 \rightarrow 3) backbone with β -(1 \rightarrow 6) side chains, making them highly branched and insoluble in water, whereas bacterial β -glucans, such as curdlan, are linear and form gelatinous structures upon heating. These structural features influence their physicochemical properties and interactions with biological receptors (Figure 1) [13,14].

The degree of branching, molecular weight, and solubility of β -glucans also affect their ability to modulate immune responses. They are recognized by receptors such as dectin-1 and CR3, activating NF- κ B and MAPK signaling pathways, which stimulate phagocytosis, cytokine production, and the activity of natural killer cells and macrophages [15].

In addition to their immunomodulatory effects, β -glucans exhibit antioxidant, antitumor, and hypocholesterolemic properties. Their antioxidant activity is attributed to free radical scavenging and metal ion chelation, while antitumor effects are mediated through the stimulation of immune surveillance and cytotoxic activity, enhancing the efficacy of monoclonal antibodies in cancer therapy [16].

From a metabolic perspective, microbial β -glucans display prebiotic activity, modulating the gut microbiota by selectively promoting beneficial bacteria such as *Lactobacillus casei*, *L. acidophilus*, *L. plantarum*, and *Bifidobacterium animalis subsp. lactis*, thereby supporting gastrointestinal health and systemic immune regulation. They can also slow gastric emptying and reduce postprandial glycemic spikes, making them useful in the management of type 2 diabetes and metabolic syndrome [17].

Singla et al. (2024) reviewed β -glucan as a soluble dietary fiber, covering its sources (oats, barley, mushrooms, yeast), structure, extraction and purification methods, bioavailability, and biofunctional properties. The review highlights β -glucan's health benefits, including immune modulation, cholesterol regulation, and gut health, and discusses its applications in the food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic industries, as well as trends in global trade [18].

The functionality of β -glucans is closely linked to their molecular structure. Triple-helix conformations and high molecular weight, common in fungal β -glucans, correlate with strong biological activity, whereas soluble fractions with lower molecular weight are easier to incorporate into food and pharmaceutical formulations, albeit with a slightly reduced bioactivity [19].

Thus, microbial β -glucans constitute a diverse group of biologically active polysaccharides whose efficacy depends on their molecular architecture. Understanding the structure–function relationship is essential for optimizing their use in health, nutrition, and pharmaceutical applications.

Figure 1. Relationship between Structural Properties and Biological Activities of β -Glucans [13, 14]

3. Production of β -Glucans from Microbial Sources

Given the ever-changing consumer preferences and awareness, especially after the Covid-19 pandemic, and the shift towards sustainable ingredients over synthetic ones, the industry is expected to grow. At the same time, manufacturers are increasingly adopting multiple sources, as well as different methods of harvesting, processing, and extracting β -glucans. Figure 2 shows the evolution of the β -glucan market worldwide, indicating a projected growth of at least 8.2% during the period 2023–2030.

Figure 2. Evolution of the global beta-glucan market [20].

Microorganisms represent a sustainable and versatile source for β -glucan production, offering significant advantages in terms of efficient cultivation, structural variability, and multifaceted bioactivity. Among microbial producers, yeasts, filamentous fungi, and certain bacterial species serve as potential sources of β -glucans with specific molecular architectures and functional properties [21].

3.1 Yeasts

Yeasts, particularly *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, constitute one of the most important and widely used industrial sources of β -glucans. Their cell wall can contain up to 60% β -glucans, predominantly composed of glucose units linked by β -(1 \rightarrow 3) linkages, branched through β -(1 \rightarrow 6) side chains (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Schematic positioning of β -glucans in the cell wall of the yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* [22]

These polysaccharides are located in the inner layer of the cell wall and play a key role in maintaining cellular structural integrity. β -Glucans extracted from yeasts exhibit strong immunomodulatory potential, capable of activating critical immune receptors such as dectin-1, TLRs, and CR3 [23]. With GRAS (generally recognized as safe) status, these compounds are widely utilized in the functional food, dietary supplement, and pharmaceutical industries [24].

Another source of β -glucans is the yeast sediment resulting from winemaking. It is known that 100 kg of processed grapes generate approximately 20–25 kg of pomace, 3–5 kg of stems and 8–10 kg of yeast sediment, depending on the grape variety and the winemaking methods applied [25]. Wine yeast sediment can be classified into three groups depending on the stage of winemaking: primary and secondary fermentation yeast, formed during alcoholic and malolactic fermentation, and maturation yeast, formed during wine maturation. On the other hand, wine yeast sediments can also be classified according to particle size: heavy yeast sediments (between 100 μ m and 2 mm, which settle within 24 hours) and light yeast sediments (<100 μ m, between 1 and 24 μ m, and which remain in suspension at least 24 hours).

after shaking). Wine yeast sediment is defined as “the sediment that settles in winemaking tanks after fermentation, during storage or after authorized treatment or that is obtained after filtering or centrifuging the wine” [26]. If residual yeasts from the brewing industry are already valorized for the extraction of β -glucans, yeast extracts or dried brewer's yeast, residual yeast sediments from winemaking are largely used for the recovery of ethyl alcohol and tartaric acid [27]. The aforementioned contribute to opening up prospects for the utilization of residual yeasts from winemaking in order to obtain various multifunctional agents, including β -glucans [28]. β -glucans are located in the cell wall of yeast cells, which consists of approximately 85%–90% water-soluble mannans, 10%–48% alkali-soluble glucans, 15%–48% alkali-insoluble glucans, along with minor amounts of chitin. Due to the rigidity and thickness of the cell wall, *S. cerevisiae* cells exhibit strong resistance to lytic treatments, and certain individual processes are insufficient for effective cell wall disruption. The extraction of β -glucans from residual yeast therefore requires multiple sequential steps [29].

3.2 Fungi

Fungi, including edible and medicinal species such as *Lentinula edodes*, *Pleurotus ostreatus*, and *Ganoderma lucidum*, are also important sources of β -glucans, characterized by diverse branching patterns and variable molecular weights. In many cases, these polysaccharides form triple-helix structures, which are associated with enhanced biological activities, particularly immunostimulatory and antitumor effects [30]. Structurally, fungal β -glucans typically possess a β -(1 \rightarrow 3) backbone with β -(1 \rightarrow 6) linkages, while in some species additional linkages, such as β -(1 \rightarrow 4), have been identified (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Schematic representation of the composition of the fungal cell wall [31].

Recent studies have also highlighted their antioxidant and prebiotic properties, providing high potential for development into nutraceuticals and products aimed at maintaining intestinal health [32].

Furthermore, fungal β -glucans demonstrate significant bioactive potential and are widely employed in the nutritional sector as dietary supplements. In traditional Chinese medicine, β -glucans have been reported to modulate the immune system, exerting both stimulatory and suppressive effects, not only in healthy individuals but also in those undergoing recovery and convalescence. Among them, pleuran, a polysaccharide isolated from the oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*), has been recognized as a functional dietary

supplement that contributes to strengthening the immune response and alleviating early symptoms of fatigue and exhaustion in both adults and children. Notably, *Pleurotus ostreatus* and shiitake (*Lentinula edodes*) are considered major dietary sources of β -glucans (Figure 5) [33].

Figure 5. Edible mushrooms shiitake (*Lentinula edodes*) and oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) with their characteristic β -glucan structures [33].

Thus, immunological and biotechnological methods used recently provide a deeper understanding of the functions of fungal β -glucans. At the same time, more and more unclear aspects remain related to the classification of fungal and mushroom β -glucans and their standardization.

3.3 Bacteria

Although less commonly used in the commercial production of β -glucans, bacteria represent a source of polysaccharides with distinct structures. *Agrobacterium* species produce curdlan, a linear β -(1 \rightarrow 3)-glucan capable of forming gels upon heating, with promising applications as a pharmaceutical excipient and as a texturizing agent in the food industry [34]. Several bacterial species, including *Rhizobium radiobacter* and various *Bacillus* spp., are capable of synthesizing β -glucans with unique physicochemical and bioactive properties. These microbial β -glucans have attracted considerable attention in the field of biomedical engineering due to their biocompatibility, tunable rheological behavior, and immunomodulatory potential. Specifically, they have been applied in wound healing formulations, where their viscoelasticity supports tissue regeneration and provides a protective barrier, as well as in advanced drug delivery systems, where their bioactivity and structural versatility enable controlled release and targeted delivery of therapeutic agents. The combination of these functional characteristics makes bacterial β -glucans promising candidates for novel biomedical applications and highlights the importance of understanding

their molecular structure-function relationships for optimized utilization [35]. Furthermore, bacterial β -glucans are notable for their unbranched structure and high purity, facilitating downstream processing and offering promising avenues for application.

In conclusion, we can mention that scientific evidence indicates that the microbial origin of β -glucans significantly influences both their structural characteristics and their potential applications. Currently, yeast-derived β -glucans dominate the nutraceutical market, while fungal β -glucans are increasingly applied in medicine and cosmetology. Bacterial glucans, in turn, are valued for their specific physicochemical properties. Continuous optimization of extraction systems, together with advances in their molecular characterization, will further support the extensive use of microbial β -glucans in various fields such as health, human nutrition, cosmetics and others [36].

4. Principles of Microbial β -Glucan Synthesis

Microbial β -glucans are obtained through fermentation and represent a renewable source of polysaccharides that is easily scalable, with numerous applications across various fields. Most often, production efficiency depends on the source strain, the type of fermentation system, culture conditions, and the composition of the growth medium.

To obtain high-quality β -glucans, it is necessary to highlight strategies for optimizing the production process. The general workflow of microbial β -glucan production includes the following basic steps: selection of the microbial strain, fermentation, biomass pretreatment (cell disruption), extraction (hot water, alkaline, enzymatic), purification (precipitation, dialysis, filtration), and characterization (molecular weight, branching, bioactivity) [2].

5. Characterization of β -Glucan Extraction Methods

The production of β -glucans includes several basic steps, such as: pretreatment, cell lysis, extraction, final purification, drying, which are presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Schematic Overview of β -Glucan Production from a Microbiological Source.

β -Glucans can be obtained using selective extraction techniques that aim to preserve their structural integrity and, in particular, their bioactivity. Currently, various methods are used, each differing in terms of efficiency and impact on the molecular structure of β -glucans. At present, the most commonly used methods remain hot water extraction and enzymatic extraction [37].

5.1 Hot Water Extraction (HWE)

HWE is one of the most established techniques for isolating β -glucans from microbial or fungal biomass. The process involves immersing the biomass in water at 80–100°C, which promotes the solubilization of polysaccharides by weakening intermolecular hydrogen bonds and disrupting the cell wall matrix.

Li et al. (2025) reviewed pressurized HWE for polysaccharides, highlighting its efficiency, eco-friendliness, and ability to preserve bioactivity. Polysaccharides HWE improves extraction yields and maintains structural integrity, influencing physicochemical properties such as solubility, viscosity, and gelling capacity. These changes enhance antioxidant, immunomodulatory, and prebiotic activities. The review also discusses applications in food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic industries, as well as current challenges and future research directions for HWE [38].

Swamy et al. (2025) provided a detailed analysis of rye fiber, focusing on its extraction using Hot Water Extraction (HWE), an eco-friendly and efficient method. This technique allows the recovery of β -glucan from the rye cell wall while preserving its structure and bioactivity. HWE influences the physicochemical properties of β -glucan, such as solubility and gelling capacity, and enhances its antioxidant and immunomodulatory activities. The research highlights the applications of rye β -glucan in the food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic industries, as well as the challenges and future research directions in this field [39].

HWE is simple and cost-effective but may lead to partial degradation of β -glucans and to limited extraction efficiency for highly branched or insoluble fractions [40].

5.2 Enzymatic Extraction (EE)

EE employs specific enzymes, such as glucanases or proteases, to selectively degrade cell wall components and release β -glucans. This method allows better preservation of bioactive structures and higher selectivity compared to HWE. However, successful extraction requires careful optimization of enzyme type, concentration, temperature, and pH to maximize yield while maintaining molecular integrity.

The choice of extraction method largely depends on the β -glucan source, the desired purity, structural characteristics, and intended applications. Recent advances focus on enhancing yield and preserving bioactivity through mild, eco-friendly strategies, including combinations of enzymatic treatment with physical or chemical pretreatments [41].

Jurkaninová et al. reviewed cereal β -D-glucans, focusing on extraction methods, processing effects, and applications in food and nanotechnology. Hot water, alkaline, and enzymatic extractions preserve β -D-glucan bioactivity, although yield and purity can be limited. Cereal processing, including baking, germination, and extrusion, affects functional properties. In food, β -D-glucans are used as thickeners, stabilizers, and gelling agents. In nanotechnology, they form nanogels and nanoparticles with potential for controlled drug delivery and antimicrobial applications [42].

It is worth mentioning that recent studies show that combining the HWE method with ultrasonication or microwave irradiation increases the yield and reduces the extraction time.

Thus, Chioru et al. (2024) highlighted that the simultaneous application of hot water and ultrasound facilitates the disruption of the cellular structures of secondary wine yeast, accelerating the release of β -glucans and optimizing the extraction without compromising the integrity of the polysaccharides [43].

To obtain β -glucans without causing structural changes, it is recommended to use specific hydrolases such as β -glucanase, protease or cellulase. These enzymatic methods have a number of advantages, namely: mild conditions that preserve the molecular mass and do not influence the bioactivity of β -glucans; polysaccharides with a high degree of purity are obtained; biodegradable and environmentally friendly process.

Among the disadvantages of this method are the following: enzymes can be expensive and sensitive to handling conditions; extraction time is longer compared to chemical methods; enzymatic activity varies depending on the source of origin. All these limitations contribute negatively to the effectiveness of the extraction process.

Enzymatic extraction is an accessible and commonly used method, often combined with physical or chemical treatments to reduce processing time and the amount of enzymes required. Strategies such as enzyme immobilization and recycling contribute to cost reduction. Chioru et al. showed that enzymatic pretreatment facilitates the isolation of cellulose fibers, indirectly improving the extraction of β -glucans and the quality of composite materials [28].

In response to the limitations of conventional extraction methods—such as long processing times, high solvent consumption, and sometimes low selectivity—modern extraction technologies that use physical energies or environmentally friendly solvents have attracted significant attention. These techniques aim to maximize the yield and purity of β -glucans, while reducing environmental impact and maintaining molecular integrity.

5.3 Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction (UAE)

Another efficient approach is UAE, which relies on the phenomenon of acoustic cavitation. The formation and collapse of microbubbles in proximity to microbial or fungal cell walls induce physical disruption, thereby enhancing mass transfer. This mechanism facilitates the release of β -glucans embedded within the cell matrix. UAE enables a substantial reduction in extraction time, decreasing it from several hours to just minutes, and can lower solvent consumption by up to 50% compared with conventional hot water extraction. Extraction yields of β -glucans may increase by up to 40%, depending on the ultrasound intensity, treatment duration, and the solvent system employed [44].

However, excessive ultrasound power or prolonged exposure can compromise the functional properties of β -glucans, including viscosity and bioactivity, through cleavage of polysaccharide chains and a consequent reduction in molecular weight. Therefore, careful optimization of sonication parameters is critical to achieve a balance between enhanced extraction yield and the preservation of the structural integrity of β -glucans [45].

5.4 Microwave-Assisted Extraction (MAE)

MAE utilizes electromagnetic radiation to generate rapid and uniform heating of intracellular water, creating elevated pressure within microbial or fungal cells and thereby promoting cell wall disruption. This process facilitates the efficient release of β -glucans into the extraction medium. Compared to conventional thermal methods, MAE markedly decreases extraction time—from hours to minutes—while enhancing both yield and energy efficiency.

The study by Lertworapreecha et al. investigated the optimal growth conditions of *Lignosus rhinocerus* mycelium for β -glucan production. The authors applied microwave-assisted extraction to isolate the polysaccharides and evaluated their antioxidant activity. The results demonstrated that optimizing culture factors and using this extraction method contributed to obtaining β -glucan fractions with high bioactive potential [46].

In summary, the maximization of β -glucan extraction yield while ensuring the preservation of their molecular integrity and biological functionality requires precise control of extraction parameters, including microwave power, pulse duration, and temperature. Equally important, the choice of solvent represents a determining factor for achieving both efficiency and selectivity in β -glucan recovery, as demonstrated in several studies employing microwave-assisted extraction strategies [41].

5.5 Supercritical Fluid Extraction (SFE)

Supercritical Fluid Extraction (SFE), particularly when employing supercritical CO₂ in combination with polar co-solvents such as ethanol or water, constitutes an advanced solvent-free technique distinguished by its tunable solvating capacity and mild processing conditions. Although initially developed for the recovery of lipophilic compounds, its application in the extraction of polysaccharides, including β -glucans, has gained increasing attention in recent years. SFE enables the selective isolation of β -glucans with minimal co-extraction of unwanted cellular constituents, thereby yielding products of elevated purity [47].

The principal advantages of SFE lie in its environmentally sustainable character and its capacity to preserve the structural integrity and bioactivity of polysaccharides through the avoidance of aggressive solvents and excessive thermal treatment. Nevertheless, the broader implementation of this technique at an industrial scale remains constrained by substantial operational costs and technological complexities.

5.6 Combined and Hybrid Extraction Techniques

Recently, hybrid extraction methods, which integrate physical techniques (e.g., ultrasound or microwaves) with enzymatic or chemical pretreatments, have demonstrated synergistic effects on extraction efficiency and β -glucan purity. For instance, Chioru et al. successfully applied ultrasound-assisted alkaline extraction to enhance the yield and purity of β -glucans from residual yeasts obtained during wine fermentation processes, showing that the combination of sonication with controlled alkaline conditions intensifies cell wall disruption and polysaccharide solubilization [48].

Other combinations, such as microwave-assisted enzymatic extraction or ultrasound-assisted enzymatic treatment, have been reported to increase yields by over 50% while preserving high molecular weight and bioactivity of β -glucans. These hybrid approaches also reduce extraction time and solvent consumption compared with individual extraction methods.

In recent years, combined extraction methods that integrate physical techniques (such as ultrasound or microwaves) with enzymatic or chemical pretreatments have demonstrated positive effects on extraction efficiency and β -glucan purity. For example, Chioru et al. reported that ultrasound-assisted alkaline extraction increased both the yield and purity of β -glucans from residual yeasts obtained during wine fermentation, highlighting that the combination of sonication with controlled alkaline conditions promotes cell wall disruption and polysaccharide solubilization [48].

Additionally, combinations such as microwave-assisted enzymatic extraction or ultrasound-assisted enzymatic treatment have been shown to enhance yields by over 50% while maintaining the molecular weight and bioactivity of β -glucans. Furthermore, these hybrid approaches reduce both solvent consumption and extraction time compared with the application of individual methods [49].

6. Purification and Fractionation of β -Glucans

Extraction of β -glucans from microbial, fungal, or plant sources often yields crude preparations comprising a complex mixture of polysaccharides, proteins, lipids, phenolic compounds, and other cell wall components. In this context, purification and fractionation processes are essential to isolate β -glucans with high purity and well-defined molecular properties, which are required for applications in the food, cosmetic, and pharmaceutical sectors. Various purification methods can be employed, including precipitation, dialysis, membrane filtration, chromatographic techniques, as well as strategies for the removal of contaminants.

Boiștean et al. noted that the purity and physicochemical properties of β -glucans are influenced by the extraction method employed. This study compared processes for producing β -glucans from wine yeast lees and provides insight into their value as a by-product of winemaking, as well as their potential applications in the food industry [50].

Precipitation is one of the simplest and most commonly applied methods for the purification and fractionation of polysaccharides. Its principle is based on the differential solubility of β -glucans in aqueous or organic solvents, allowing their separation from proteins, salts, and low-molecular-weight compounds. Precipitation is most frequently performed using ethanol or ammonium sulfate [51].

Ethanol precipitation relies on the low solubility of β -glucans in organic solvents, which induces their aggregation and sedimentation. In practice, crude extracts are mixed with cold ethanol (70–90% v/v) in a ratio of 2–4 volumes of ethanol per volume of extract and maintained at 4 °C for several hours or overnight [52]. The resulting polysaccharide precipitate, typically gelatinous, is subsequently separated by centrifugation or filtration. This method is effective for concentrating β -glucans and partially removing proteins and low-molecular-weight compounds. However, the level of purity depends on the composition of the initial extract and may require repeated precipitation cycles or additional purification steps. Furthermore, ethanol precipitation allows for fractionation based on differences in solubility. By adjusting the ethanol concentration, low-molecular-weight or more hydrophobic fractions remain soluble, while higher-molecular-weight β -glucans precipitate, enabling the isolation of fractions with distinct molecular properties and biological activities.

Ammonium sulfate precipitation, although primarily used for proteins, can also be applied to polysaccharide purification to remove contaminating proteins. In this process, soluble β -glucans precipitate due to their hydrophobic nature, the high ionic strength, and the salting-out effect. This pretreatment step is typically applied prior to ethanol precipitation or chromatographic purification and is recommended for crude extracts with high protein content, which could interfere with laboratory analyses or subsequent applications.

7. Food Safety

β -glucans from yeast are recognized by the Food and Drug Administration as safe and are recommended for use in doses of up to 3 g/day. In 2011, β -glucans obtained from yeast

began to be marketed in the European Community [53]. The European Food Safety Authority assessed β -glucans as a safe product, which can be used in food supplements, in a proportion of 375 mg/day or up to 600 mg/day. In 2019, the 2017 European Union Directive was revised in which the use of β -glucans from the yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was extended to other foods, such as; breakfast cereals - 15.3 g/kg, juice drinks - 1.3 g/kg, biscuits - 6.7 g/kg, powdered milk - 25.5 g/kg and up to 3.8 g/kg in dairy products [54].

7.1 Microbial Safety Considerations

The microbial safety of β -glucan preparations is a critical aspect of food quality and consumer protection. Although the microbial strains commonly used for production, such as *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, are classified as non-pathogenic and widely recognized as safe, the risk of contamination cannot be completely eliminated. Contamination may occur at various stages of the production process, including fermentation, downstream processing (extraction and purification), storage, and packaging. Potential contaminants include opportunistic pathogenic bacteria, spoilage microorganisms, and mycotoxin-producing fungi, which can compromise both the safety and quality of the final product [55].

To mitigate these risks, Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) are implemented to ensure that facilities, equipment, and production protocols maintain strict hygiene standards. Additionally, Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP) frameworks are employed to identify, monitor, and control critical points where microbial contamination could occur. These include monitoring fermentation vessels, sterilization of culture media, and proper handling of raw materials and finished products.

The safety of β -glucans largely depends on rigorous microbial testing throughout production and handling. Routine analyses include total aerobic microbial counts, yeast and mold counts, coliforms, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella spp.*, and other potential contaminants. In addition to these conventional methods, advanced techniques such as PCR-based detection of specific pathogens are increasingly used to ensure high sensitivity and reliability. The study by Neun et al. emphasizes the importance of these approaches for detecting β -glucan contamination in nanotechnology-based formulations, highlighting the need for strict microbial control protocols to safeguard product safety and quality [56].

Maintaining the microbial safety of β -glucans is critical for their quality and efficacy. β -Glucan powders and extracts are hygroscopic and sensitive to storage conditions; exposure to moisture, inappropriate temperatures, or improper handling can promote microbial growth and compromise product integrity. Careful control of water activity, the use of airtight and sterile packaging, and cold-chain maintenance when necessary are essential measures to prevent post-production contamination. The study by Loving et al. highlights the importance of these practices in the context of β -glucan applications in animal nutrition and health. The authors demonstrated that dietary β -glucan supplementation can influence intestinal microbial diversity and the efficacy of *Salmonella* vaccination in pigs, emphasizing that preserving product integrity and safety is crucial for supporting the immunomodulatory and functional effects of β -glucans. Proper storage and packaging not only protect the product from contamination but also help maximize its biological benefits [57].

In conclusion, ensuring microbial safety in β -glucan preparations requires a comprehensive, multi-level approach encompassing facility hygiene, process control, rigorous testing, and proper storage. Adherence to these practices is essential to guarantee

that β -glucan-containing products are safe for human consumption and comply with international food safety regulations.

7.2 Allergens and Immunogenicity

Although β -glucans are widely recognized as safe food ingredients, their intrinsic immunomodulatory properties require careful consideration, particularly in sensitive populations. β -Glucans are biologically active polysaccharides that can interact with pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) of the innate immune system, such as Dectin-1, complement receptor 3 (CR3), and Toll-like receptors (TLRs). Upon binding to these receptors, β -glucans can activate a range of immune responses, including phagocytosis, production of reactive oxygen species, and cytokine secretion, which collectively enhance the body's defense against pathogens [58,59].

Turkbey et al. (2025) evaluated the immune response of airway epithelial cells to β -glucans derived from *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Candida albicans* in a Th17 cytokine environment. The study showed that *C. albicans* β -glucans reduced the viability of bronchial epithelial cells more than those from *A. fumigatus*, while Dectin-1 receptor expression was differentially modulated by IL-17: decreasing in nasal epithelial cells and increasing in bronchial cells. Furthermore, *A. fumigatus* β -glucans, in the presence of IL-17, amplified the production of proinflammatory cytokines such as IL-6 and IL-8. These results highlight the role of Th17 cytokines in modulating epithelial responses to fungal β -glucans, providing insights for the development of strategies to prevent respiratory fungal infections [60].

Rainer et al. (2024) examined the immunomodulatory effects of six commercial β -glucans on mouse myeloid dendritic cells. All β -glucans activated the Dectin-1 receptor, while TLR2 was mainly triggered by Zymosan. They induced differential cytokine secretion and upregulated activation markers (CD40, CD80, CD86, MHCII). In co-cultures with allergen-primed Th2 CD4+ T cells, β -glucans suppressed IL-5 secretion, with only Zymosan and β -1,3-glucan reducing IFN γ . These findings highlight the distinct immune-modulating properties of β -glucans, supporting their potential as adjuvants in allergy therapy [61].

Marchi et al. (2025) reported a case of a cutaneous allergic reaction in a 6-year-old obese mixed-breed dog after consuming purified β -1,3/1,6-glucans derived from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (0.1%). Symptoms included severe pruritus, alopecia, and erythema, which rapidly improved when the dog was switched to a control diet without β -glucans. Reintroduction of β -glucans triggered recurrence of the symptoms, which again subsided upon returning to the control diet. Additionally, the dog showed dermatological signs after ingesting β -1,3-glucans from *Euglena gracilis*, although confirmation was not definitive due to the lack of a challenge test. This case highlights the potential risks of β -glucans as nutraceuticals in canine diets, even at low doses [62].

While these immunostimulatory effects are beneficial in healthy individuals, they can pose potential risks for susceptible populations, such as individuals with autoimmune disorders, allergies, or heightened inflammatory responses. In rare cases, excessive or uncontrolled activation of the immune system may exacerbate hypersensitivity reactions, leading to symptoms such as skin rashes, gastrointestinal discomfort, or respiratory issues [63,64].

To mitigate these risks, several safety measures are recommended:

1. **Proper labeling** – Clear declaration of β -glucan content and source (e.g., yeast, cereal, or fungal origin) to inform consumers and healthcare providers.

2. **Dose regulation** – Establishing limits for daily intake based on clinical evidence and regulatory guidance, as excessive doses may increase the likelihood of immune overstimulation.
3. **Clinical evaluation** – Pre-market studies to assess potential allergenicity and immunogenicity, particularly for novel β -glucan formulations or highly concentrated extracts.
4. **Post-market monitoring** – Implementing surveillance systems for adverse reactions and collection of real-world safety data to refine usage guidelines.

Additionally, research into the structure-function relationship of β -glucans indicates that molecular weight, degree of branching, solubility, and source can influence their immunogenic potential. Highly purified, well-characterized β -glucans are generally less likely to trigger adverse immune reactions, whereas crude or partially purified extracts may contain residual proteins or other bioactive compounds that increase immunogenicity [65].

In summary, while β -glucans are safe for general consumption and offer notable immunological benefits, careful attention to source selection, purification, formulation, and dosing is essential to minimize the risk of allergenicity and unintended immune activation. Continued research into their immunomodulatory mechanisms and clinical safety will further support their responsible use in functional foods, dietary supplements, and therapeutic applications.

Conclusions

Microbial β -glucans are structurally diverse polysaccharides, whose biological activity—immunomodulatory, antioxidant, and prebiotic—depend on molecular weight, branching, and source of origin. Efficient production from microorganisms relies on optimization of fermentation, understanding of biosynthesis, and strain selection. Extraction methods, including HWE, UAE, and PHWE, etc., strongly influence yield, purity, and bioactivity. The degree of purification ensures the functional integrity of β -glucans in various applications. Regulatory evaluations confirm their safety in foods and supplements, but microbial contamination and immunogenic potential require careful management through GMP, HACCP, and appropriate labeling. Overall, microbial β -glucans offer significant potential in food, pharmaceutical, and biomedical applications, and future research should aim to improve production, standardize analytical characterization, and expand clinical evidence.

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References

1. Lante, A.; Canazza, E.; Tessari, P. Beta-Glucans of Cereals: Functional and Technological Properties. *Nutrients* 2023, 15, 2124. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu15092124>
2. Singla, A.; Gupta, O.P.; Sagwal, V.; Kumar, R.; Kumar, V.; Awasthi, P.; Kumar, N. Beta-Glucan as a Soluble Dietary Fiber Source: Origins, Biosynthesis, Extraction, Purification, Structural Characteristics, Bioavailability, Biofunctional Attributes, Industrial Utilization, and Global Trade. *Nutrients* 2024, 16, 900. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu16060900>

3. Gudej, S.; Filip, R.; Harasym, J.; Skrzypczak-Zielinska, M.; Wilk, M.; Gromadzka-Ostrowska, J. Clinical Outcomes after Oat Beta-Glucans Dietary Treatment in Gastritis Patients. *Nutrients* 2021, 13, 2791. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu13082791>
4. De Marco Castro, E.; Calder, P.C.; Roche, H.M. β -1,3/1,6-Glucans and Immunity: State of the Art and Future Directions. *Mol. Nutr. Food Res.* 2021, 65, e1901071. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mnfr.201901071>
5. Cerami, E.G.; Gross, B.E.; Demir, E.; Rodchenkov, I.; Babur, O.; Anwar, N.; Schultz, N.; Sander, C.; Bader, G.D. Pathway Commons, a Web Resource for Biological Pathway Data. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2011, 39, D685–D690. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkq1039>
6. Rodchenkov, I.; Babur, O.; Luna, A.; Aksoy, B.A.; Wong, J.V.; Fong, D.; Franz, M.; Siper, M.C.; Cheung, M.; Wrana, M.; et al. Pathway Commons 2019 Update: Integration, Analysis and Exploration of Pathway Data. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2020, 48, D489–D497. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkz946>
7. Vetvicka, V.; Vetvickova, J. Anti-Infectious and Anti-Tumor Activities of β -Glucans. *Anticancer Res.* 2020, 40, 3139–3145. <https://doi.org/10.21873/anticancer.14295>
8. Boiștean, A.; Chirsanova, A. Exploring the Physical and Qualitative Characteristics of Muffins with the Addition of Yeast Wine Sediment. In *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Construction, Design, Technology and Optimization of Machines in the Building Field (OPROTEH)*; Alma Mater: Bacău, Romania, 2025; pp. 121–122.
9. Li, X.; Wu, Y.; Duan, R.; Chen, F.; Li, L.; Huang, J. Research Progress in the Extraction, Structural Characteristics, Bioactivity, and Commercial Applications of Oat β -Glucan: A Review. *Foods* 2024, 13, 4160. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods13244160>
10. Zhu, Y.; Dong, L.; Huang, L.; Shi, W.; Chen, Y.; Li, Y. Effects of Oat β -Glucan, Oat Resistant Starch, and the Whole Oat Flour on Insulin Resistance, Inflammation, and Gut Microbiota in High-Fat-Diet-Induced Type 2 Diabetic Rats. *J. Funct. Foods* 2020, 69, 103939. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jff.2020.103939>
11. Chirsanova, A.; Siminiuc, R.; Reșitca, V.; Țurcanu, A.; Ciorbă, L.; Ursu, L. Front-of-Pack Labeling of Food Products: Evolution, Characteristics, Challenges and Prospects. *J. Soc. Sci.* 2025, 8, 28–45. [https://doi.org/10.52326/jss.utm.2025.8\(2\).03](https://doi.org/10.52326/jss.utm.2025.8(2).03)
12. Han, B.; Baruah, K.; Cox, E.; Vanrompay, D. Structure–Functional Activity Relationship of β -Glucans from the Perspective of Immunomodulation: A Mini-Review. *Front. Immunol.* 2020, 11, 658. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2020.00658>
13. Naseer Sadiq, B.; Fadel Mousa, E. Production of Nano Beta-Glucans from Baking Yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and Its Comparison with Extracted Beta-Glucans. *IOP Conf. Ser. Earth Environ. Sci.* 2024, 1325, 012049. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1325/1/012049>
14. Yu, C.; Chen, H.; Du, D.; Peng, J.; He, Y.; Zhang, Y. β -Glucan from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* Alleviates Oxidative Stress in LPS-Stimulated RAW264.7 Cells via Dectin-1/Nrf2/HO-1 Signaling Pathway. *Cell Stress Chaperones* 2021, 26, 629–637. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12192-021-01205-5>
15. Edo, G.I.; Mafe, A.N.; Ali, A.B.M.; Chukwuma, C.I.; Ayeni, E.A. A Critical Review on the Impacts of β -Glucans on Gut Microbiota and Human Health. *The Microbe* 2025, 7, 100394. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microb.2025.100394>
16. Rohilla, S.; Jaiswal, A.; Bora, J.; Sharma, M. Sources of Beta-Glucan. In *Beta-Glucan: Sources, Properties and Applications*; Bashir Mir, M., Mir, S.A., Eds.; Springer Nature, Cham, Switzerland, 2025, pp. 11–25.
17. Moghadam, B.E.; Hasebi, Z.; Seyfzadeh, S.; Maleki, R.; Zarei, M. Barley β -Glucan for Conjugated Linoleic Acid (CLA) Production by *Bifidobacterium animalis* subsp. *lactis*: Fatty Acid Variation and Bacterial Viability Study. *Bioact. Carbohydr. Diet. Fibre* 2022, 28, 100321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bcdf.2022.100321>
18. Singh, E.; Vasishta, P.; Singla, A. AI-Enhanced Education: Exploring the Impact of AI Literacy on Generation Z's Academic Performance in Northern India. *Qual. Assur. Educ.* 2024, 33, pp. 185–202. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QAE-02-2024-0037>
19. Bobade, H.; Gupta, A.; Sharma, S. Beta-Glucan. In *Nutraceuticals and Health Care*; Elsevier, Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 2022, pp. 343–358.
20. Beta Glucan Market Size, Share & Trends Analysis Report by Source, by Type, by Application, by Region, and Segment Forecasts, 2024–2030; Grand View Research: San Francisco, CA, USA. Available online: <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/beta-glucan-market/methodology> (accessed on 10 October 2025).
21. Venkatachalam, G.; Arumugam, S.; Doble, M. Industrial Production and Applications of α/β Linear and Branched Glucans. *Indian Chem. Eng.* 2021, 63, pp. 533–547. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00194506.2020.1798820>

22. Orlean, P. Architecture and Biosynthesis of the *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* Cell Wall. *Genetics* 2012, 192, pp. 775–818. <https://doi.org/10.1534/genetics.112.144485>
23. Murphy, E.J.; Rezoagli, E.; Collins, C.; McAuliffe, J.; Owens, E.; Boyce, K.; Rowan, N.J. Sustainable Production and Pharmaceutical Applications of β -Glucan from Microbial Sources. *Microbiol. Res.* 2023, 274, 127424. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micres.2023.127424>
24. Günal-Köroğlu, D.; Karabulut, G.; Mohammadian, F.; Gulec, H.A.; Cekmecelioglu, D. Production of Yeast Cell Wall Polysaccharides— β -Glucan and Chitin by Using Food Waste Substrates: Biosynthesis, Production, Extraction, and Purification Methods. *Compr. Rev. Food Sci. Food Saf.* 2025, 24, e70161. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.70161>
25. Ye, Z.; Qin, Y.; Harrison, R.; Huang, Y.; Tian, T. Characterization of Bioactive Compounds in Lees from New Zealand Wines with Different Vinification Backgrounds. *Antioxidants* 2022, 11, 2335. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox11122335>
26. Athanasiou, P.E.; Patila, M.; Fotiadou, R.; Lymperopoulou, T.; Tzouvelekis, L.S.; Anastasopoulou, A.; Lalas, S. Valorization of Wine Lees: Assessment of Antioxidant, Antimicrobial and Enzyme Inhibitory Activity of Wine Lees Extract and Incorporation in Chitosan Films. *Waste Biomass Valorization* 2024, 15, pp. 5657–5672. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12649-024-02524-1>
27. Jamali, H.R.; Steel, C.C.; Mohammadi, E. Wine Research and Its Relationship with Wine Production: A Scientometric Analysis of Global Trends. *Aust. J. Grape Wine Res.* 2020, 26, pp. 130–138. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajgw.12422>
28. Chioru, A.; Chiselita, N.; Suhodol, N.; Guzun, S.; Balan, G.; Gudumac, V.; Țurcanu, A.; Chirsanova, A. Physico-Chemical and Microbiological Profile of Wine Lees of Red Wines from Local Grapes Varieties. *Food Nutr. Sci.* 2023, 14, pp. 1133–1148. <https://doi.org/10.4236/fns.2023.1411071>
29. Chioru, A.; Chirsanova, A. Obtaining β -Glucans from the Cell Wall of Residual Wine Yeast. In *Technical-Scientific Conference of Students, Master's and Doctoral Candidates*; Chișinău, Moldova, 2024, pp. 1061–1066.
30. Yehia, R.S. Evaluation of the Biological Activities of β -Glucan Isolated from *Lentinula edodes*. *Let. Appl. Microbiol.* 2022, 75, pp. 317–329. <https://doi.org/10.1111/lam.13727>
31. Fesel, P.H.; Zuccaro, A. β -Glucan: Crucial Component of the Fungal Cell Wall and Elusive MAMP in Plants. *Fungal Genet. Biol.* 2016, 90, pp. 53–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fgb.2015.12.004>
32. El-Maradny, Y.A.; Abouakkada, A.S.; Abbass, A.A.G.; Hafez, S.M.; Mohamed, A.I.; Ahmed, S.A. Prebiotic Properties and Antioxidant Effect of Crude Extracts and Polysaccharides from *Agaricus bisporus* and *Pleurotus ostreatus* Mushrooms. *Sci. Rep.* 2025, 15, 31113. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-16152-9>
33. van Steenwijk, H.P.; Bast, A.; de Boer, A. Immunomodulating Effects of Fungal Beta-Glucans: From Traditional Use to Medicine. *Nutrients* 2021, 13, 1333. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu13041333>
34. Ping, Z.; Deng, L.; Liu, H.; Zhang, J.; Li, S. Branching Structure and Chain Conformation of Water-Soluble L- β -Galactoglucan Extracted from *Agrobacterium pusense*. *SSRN Preprint* 2025. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5384063>
35. Huang, H.; Wen, Y.; Li, Z.; Zhang, Y.; Wu, X.; Zhang, W.; Chen, Y. Characterization and Rheological Properties of a New Exopolysaccharide Overproduced by *Rhizobium* sp. L01. *Polymers* 2025, 17, 592. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym17050592>
36. Fehrenbach, G.W.; Tanoeiro, J.R.; Pogue, R.; Lewis, C.; Foster, S. Beta-Glucan-Enriched Diets Improve Immune Function, Antioxidant Activity, and Survivability in Challenged Oysters. *Food Hydrocoll. Health* 2025, 8, 100227. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fhfh.2025.100227>
37. Boiștean, A.; Chirsanova, A.; Chioru, A. Production of β -Glucan from Yeast Lees of Local Wines Produced Using Different Technologies. In *National Scientific Conference "Innovation: A Factor of Socio-Economic Development"*; Universitatea de Stat „Bogdan Petriceicu Hasdeu”: Cahul, Republic of Moldova, 2024, pp. 45–46.
38. Li, J.; Ye, G.; Wang, J.; Liu, S.; Zhao, X.; Fang, Y. Recent Advances in Pressurized Hot Water Extraction/Modification of Polysaccharides: Structure, Physicochemical Properties, Bioactivities, and Applications. *Compr. Rev. Food Sci. Food Saf.* 2025, 24, e70104. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.70104>
39. Swamy, C.T.; Sen, A.; Maramreddy, P.R.; Reddy, P.S. Rye Fiber: Extraction, Identification Methods and Health Benefiting Features. In *Rye: Processing, Nutritional Profile and Commercial Uses*; Singh Purewal, S., Ed.; Springer Nature, Cham, Switzerland, 2025, pp. 95–116.
40. Sakdasri, W.; Arnutpongchai, P.; Phonsavat, S.; Srikumool, M.; Kaewpiboon, C. Pressurized Hot Water Extraction of Crude Polysaccharides, β -Glucan, and Phenolic Compounds from Dried Gray Oyster Mushroom. *LWT* 2022, 168, 113895. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2022.113895>

41. Mejía, S.M.V.; De Francisco, A.; Bohrer, B.M. A Comprehensive Review on Cereal β -Glucan: Extraction, Characterization, Causes of Degradation, and Food Application. *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* 2020, 60, pp. 3693–3704. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2019.1706444>
42. Jurkaninová, L.; Dvořáček, V.; Gregusová, V.; Havrlentová, M. Cereal β -d-Glucans in Food Processing Applications and Nanotechnology Research. *Foods* 2024, 13, 500. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods13030500>
43. Chioru, A.; Trohina, A.; Boiștean, A.; Chirsanova, A. Physicochemical and Nutritional Characteristics of Winemaking Lees of Wines from Local Varieties from Republic of Moldova. In *International Conference on Global Food Security*; Leuven, Belgium, 2024.
44. Yuan, H.; He, Y.; Zhang, H.; Ma, X. Ultrasound-Assisted Enzymatic Hydrolysis of Yeast β -Glucan Catalyzed by β -Glucanase: Chemical and Microstructural Analysis. *Ultrason. Sonochem.* 2022, 86, 106012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultsonch.2022.106012>
45. Nguyen, D.T.; Nguyen, P.T.; Nguyen, B.V.; Tran, Q.H.; Pham, T.L. Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction of β -Glucan from Vietnam *Pleurotus citrinopileatus* Enhances Antioxidant Activities. *Nat. Prod. J.* 2025, 15, E200624231105. <https://doi.org/10.2174/0122103155292732240610115317>
46. Lertworapreecha, M.; Chanasit, W.; Nitipan, S.; Chamnankit, W. Growth Factors Optimization and Antioxidant Evaluation of β -Glucan Extracted from *Lignosus rhinocerus* Mycelium Using Microwave-Assisted Extraction. *Trends Sci.* 2025, 22, pp. 8912–8912. <https://doi.org/10.48048/tis.2025.8912>
47. Sargar, S.; Tiwari, S.; Reddy, G.B.; Kavitate, D. Methods of Extraction of Beta-Glucan. In *Beta-Glucan: Sources, Properties and Applications*; Bashir Mir, M., Mir, S.A., Eds.; Springer Nature, Cham, Switzerland, 2025; pp. 27–53.
48. Chioru, A.; Chirsanova, A.; Dabija, A.; Boiștean, A.; Trohina, A.; Chiselita, N.; Suhodol, N. Extraction Methods and Characterization of β -Glucans from Yeast Lees of Wines Produced Using Different Technologies. *Foods* 2024, 13, 3982. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods13243982>
49. Theint, P.P.; Sakkayawong, N.; Buajarn, S.; Singkhonrat, J. Comparative Study of Structural Integrity, Efficiency, and Convenience for Beta-Glucan Extraction Among Conventional and Microwave-Assisted Extraction: Utilizing the Domestic Microwave System. *SSRN Preprint* 2024. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4822124>
50. Boiștean, A.; Chioru, A.; Chirsanova, A. Physicochemical Properties of Beta-Glucan from Residual-Wine Yeast as Affected by Different Extraction Procedures. In *Perspectives and Problems of Integration into the European Area of Research and Education*, 11th Edition; Cahul, Republic of Moldova, 2024, 11(1), pp. 340–346.
51. Saetang, N.; Ramaraj, R.; Unpaprom, Y. Optimization of ethanol precipitation of schizophyllan from *Schizophyllum commune* by applied statistical modelling. *Biomass Convers. Biorefinery* 2024, 14, pp. 2707–2719. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-022-02384-6>
52. Maheshwari, G.; Sowrirajan, S.; Joseph, B. Extraction and Isolation of β -Glucan from Grain Sources—A Review. *J. Food Sci.* 2017, 82, 1535–1545. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1750-3841.13765>
53. EFSA. Safety of 'yeast beta-glucans', 2011. Available online: <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/2137> (accessed on 2 October 2025).
54. European Commission. Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2017/2078 of 10 November 2017 authorising the extension of use of yeast beta-glucans as a novel food ingredient in accordance with Regulation (EC) No 258/97 of the European Parliament and of the Council [notified under document number C(2017) 7391]. *Off. J. Eur. Union* 2017, L 298/9–L 298/11.
55. Markovina, N.; Banjari, I.; Bucevic Popovic, V.; et al. Efficacy and safety of oral and inhalation commercial beta-glucan products: Systematic review of randomized controlled trials. *Clin. Nutr.* 2020, 39, pp. 40–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnu.2019.01.003>
56. Neun, B.W.; Cedrone, E.; Potter, T.M.; et al. Detection of Beta-Glucan Contamination in Nanotechnology-Based Formulations. *Molecules* 2020, 25, 3367. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25153367>
57. Loving, C.L.; Bearson, S.M.D.; Bearson, B.L.; et al. Effect of dietary β -glucan on intestinal microbial diversity and *Salmonella* vaccine immunogenicity and efficacy in pigs. *Vet. Microbiol.* 2023, 278, 109648. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetmic.2022.109648>
58. Vetricka, V.; Vannucci, L.; Sima, P. β -Glucan as a new tool in vaccine development. *Scand. J. Immunol.* 2020, 91, e12833. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sji.12833>
59. Lin, Y.-J.; Zimmermann, J.; Schülke, S. Novel adjuvants in allergen-specific immunotherapy: where do we stand? *Front. Immunol.* 2024, 15, 1348305. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2024.1348305>
60. Turkbey, M.; Karaguzel, D.; Uzunkaya, A.D.; et al. The immune response of upper and lower airway epithelial cells to *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Candida albicans*-derived β -glucan in Th17 type cytokine environment. *Arch. Microbiol.* 2025, 207, 70. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00203-025-04266-7>

61. Rainer, H.; Goretzki, A.; Lin, Y.-J.; et al. Characterization of the Immune-Modulating Properties of Different β -Glucans on Myeloid Dendritic Cells. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 2024, 25, 9914. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms25189914>
62. Marchi, P.H.; Miranda, M. dos S.; Príncipe, L. de A.; et al. Allergic Reaction to Beta-Glucans in an Obese Dog: A Case Report of Confirmed and Suspected Sources. *J. Anim. Physiol. Anim. Nutr.* 2024, n/a. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpn.14111>
63. Talbott, S.M.; Talbott, J.A.; Talbott, T.L.; Dingler, E. β -Glucan supplementation, allergy symptoms, and quality of life in self-described ragweed allergy sufferers. *Food Sci. Nutr.* 2013, 1, 90–101. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fsn3.11>
64. Moreno, M.L.; Nieves, C.J.; Hebert, K.; et al. Yeast Beta-Glucan Enhances Antibody Response Following Influenza Vaccination – A Double-Blind, Randomized, Placebo-Controlled Pilot Trial. *J. Diet. Suppl.* 2025, 22, pp. 795–810. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19390211.2025.2539876>
65. Korotchenko, E.; Schießl, V.; Scheiblhofer, S.; et al. Laser-facilitated epicutaneous immunotherapy with hypoallergenic beta-glucan neoglycoconjugates suppresses lung inflammation and avoids local side effects in a mouse model of allergic asthma. *Allergy* 2021, 76, pp. 210–222. <https://doi.org/10.1111/all.14481>

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